

Supporting Information

2D Rhenium- and Niobium-Doped WSe₂ Photoactive Cathodes in Photo-Enhanced Hybrid Zn-Ion Capacitors

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Figure S1. SEM images of exfoliated (a) WSe₂, (b) Re- WSe₂, (c) Nb- WSe₂, (d) HRTEM of WSe₂, (e) HRTEM of Nb- WSe₂ (image of position in Figure S2). (f) and (g) EDX spectra of the WSe₂ and Nb-WSe₂ samples, respectively.

Figure S2. TEM images with the corresponding selected area electron (SAED) diffraction patterns of pristine WSe₂ (a, b), Re- WSe₂ (c, d), and Nb- WSe₂ (e, f).

Figure S3. UV-visible spectra of pristine WSe₂ (black), Re- WSe₂ (red), and Nb-WSe₂ (blue).

Figure S4. Tauc plots of pristine WSe₂ (a and b), Re- WSe₂ (c and d), and Nb- WSe₂ (e and f).

Figure S5. Optimized structures of **(a)** WSe₂, **(b)** Nb-WSe₂ and **(c)** Re-WSe₂.

Figure S6. Electronic band structure of **(a)** WSe₂, **(b)** Nb-WSe₂ and **(c)** Re-WSe₂. Partial and total density of states for **(d)** WSe₂, **(e)** Nb-WSe₂ and **(f)** Re-WSe₂.

Okomentoval(a): [r1]: better to add what s, p, and d stand for in d,e,f

Figure S7. BET measurements of pristine WSe₂ (black), Re- WSe₂ (red), and Nb-WSe₂ (blue) samples.

Figure S8. CV of WSe₂ in the potential range of 0 to 1.1 V, scan rate = 5 mVs⁻¹.

Figure S9. Comparison of CV curves at 100 mV s^{-1} in the dark and under illumination for (a) undoped WSe₂, (b) Re- WSe₂ and (c) Nb- WSe₂ samples.

Figure S10. Comparative galvanostatic charge-discharge curves at specific currents of 30, 50 and 100 mA g^{-1} in the dark and under irradiation of **(a, c, f)** WSe_2 , **(b, d, e)** Re-WSe_2 and **(g)** Nb-WSe_2 .

Figure S11. Fitting of Nyquist plots and equivalent circuit diagrams (insets) of (a) pristine WSe_2 , (b) $Re-WSe_2$, and (c) $Nb-WSe_2$, under dark and light irradiation (420 nm, 100 mW/cm^2).

Figure S12. Hall measurements of Re-WSe₂ (green) and Nb-WSe₂ (yellow): **(a)** Charge carrier concentration, **(b)** Hall mobility.

Figure S13. (a) Cyclic stability for 500 cycles, and (b) capacitance retention and coulombic efficiency of pristine WSe₂.

Figure S14. SEM images of the active photocathode Re-WSe₂ before (a), and after (b) stability test.

Table S1. Comparison of parameters obtained from equivalent circuit in dark and under light irradiation for WSe₂, Re-WSe₂, and Nb-WSe₂.

Sample	Dark			Light	
	Elements and Parameters	Value	Estimated Error (%)	Value	Estimated Error (%)
WSe ₂	R _s	5.4609 (Ω)	13.983	7.0042 (Ω)	3.436
	R _p	1248.7 (Ω)	3.607	746 (Ω)	2.638
	C	692 (μF)	2.764	729 (μF)	2.638
	R _p	200 (Ω)	3.631	151.32 (Ω)	2.600
	Y ₀	217 (μMho ^s ^N)	11.183	0.00017787 (μMho ^s ^N)	8.751
	N	0.55438	2.658	0.58309	1.732
	χ ²	0.14277		0.14472	
Re-WSe ₂	R _s	2.8311 (Ω)	2.265	2.9125 (Ω)	2.299
	R _p	2429.9 (Ω)	13.198	698.12 (Ω)	18.939
	CPE (Y ₀)	853 (μMho ^s ^N)	3.079	1.17 (mMho ^s ^N)	8.000
	CPE (N)	0.71493	4.595	0.77378	1.832
	R _p	90.28 (Ω)	21.478	78 (Ω)	6.729
	CPE (Y ₀)	680 (μMho ^s ^N)	8.751	1.15 (mMho ^s ^N)	3.302
	CPE (N)	0.611	9.032	0.55111	4.023
Nb-WSe ₂	χ ²	0.10593		0.082566	
	R _s	4.8138 (Ω)	1.554	4.8482 (Ω)	0.582
	R _p	2233 (Ω)	3.845	1000.1 (Ω)	1.219
	CPE (Y ₀)	0.00045154	2.273	0.00011145	1.887
	CPE (N)	0.81969	1.972	0.68307	0.330
	R _p	222.79 (Ω)	4.357	155.05(Ω)	1.289
	CPE (Y ₀)	9.9315E-05	4.469	0.00060727	0.958
	CPE (N)	0.69223	0.797	0.82033	0.740
χ ²	0.05653		0.0073664		

Table S2. Comparison of different photo-enhanced electrochemical energy storage systems.

Photo-electrochemical energy storage system	Light-wavelength	Electrolyte	Voltage response	Specific capacitance	Energy and Power-densities	Ref.
V doped ternary Zn-Ni-Co oxide nanostructure	-	KOH/PVA	-	2960 mFg ⁻¹ @ 0.02Ag ⁻¹	148 mW h kg ⁻¹ , 12000 mWKg ⁻¹ @0.02Ag ⁻¹	28
1T-WSe ₂	-	1M H ₂ SO ₄	-	2813 μFcm ⁻²	-	29
CdS/ZnO	455 nm	3M Zn(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂ aqueous electrolyte	800 mV	50 mAhg ⁻¹	30 WhKg ⁻¹ , 100 WKg ⁻¹	9
Sulfur-, tungsten-doped TiO ₂ nanotube supercapacitor	λ = 533 nm, intensity ~ 100 mW cm ⁻²	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	400 mV	31 mFg ⁻¹ @ 0.23 mAcm ⁻²	6.21 Wh cm ⁻² And 399 W cm ⁻² @ 0.23 mA cm ⁻²	30
2D g-C ₃ N ₄	λ = 420 nm, intensity ~ 50 mW cm ⁻²	2 M ZnSO ₄	850 mV	11377 mFg ⁻¹	~ 668 mWh kg ⁻¹ , 1625 mW kg ⁻¹ @ 0.005 A g ⁻¹	7
Germanane-cyanoethyl (Ge-C ₂ -CN)	λ = 435 nm, intensity ~ 50 mW cm ⁻²	2 M ZnSO ₄	1000 mV	6 Fg ⁻¹	550 mWh Kg ⁻¹ , 31000 mW Kg ⁻¹ @ 0.060 A g ⁻¹	31

Niobium Carbide MXene	$\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$, intensity $\sim 50 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$	2 M ZnSO ₄	1000 mV	27 Fg ⁻¹	2.4 Wh Kg ⁻¹ , 40 WKg ⁻¹ @ 0.030 A g ⁻¹	22
Re-WSe ₂	$\lambda = 420 \text{ nm}$, intensity $\sim 100 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$	2 M ZnSO ₄	800 mV	8.43 Fg ⁻¹	574.21 mWh Kg ⁻¹ , 5906 mW Kg ⁻¹ @ 0.015 A g ⁻¹ .	This work